

Research paper

Operational modal analysis applied to floating offshore wind turbine dynamics identification in wave basins in the presence of free-surface modes

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the modal characteristics of a 10 MW floating offshore wind turbine (FOWT) model, scaled to full size. We utilise both traditional and advanced algorithms, including logarithmic decrement, stochastic subspace identification covariance and data-driven methods, to analyse the system's operational behaviour under free decay and irregular wave conditions. This study explores the full damping matrix and the influence of coupled degrees of freedom. Under irregular wave conditions, a 30% deviation in the surge resonance frequency is identified, which is linked to the wave period's near-heave resonance and a fluid free-surface mode of the fluid inside the wave tank. The use of stability diagrams facilitates the identification of these modes from the FOWT's response. Furthermore, this paper examines the evolution of damping and operational deflection shapes across different sea states. The models synthesised from modal estimations of wave tests are validated using autocorrelation functions, which confirm that the employed methods effectively captured the FOWT's rigid-body dynamics, even in extreme conditions where the FOWT and fluid act as a coupled system. The study emphasises that free-surface modes have the potential to introduce additional energy, which could be a significant contributor to the underestimation of low-frequency responses in numerical hydrodynamic models.

1. Introduction

A floating offshore wind turbine (FOWT) is a complex system comprising a controlled rotating machine on a moored floating structure. Various coupling effects (e.g., aeroelastic, aero-servo, floater mooring and hydro-elasticity in flexible hulls) influence its dynamics (ABS, 2014). Nonlinearities arise from both natural phenomena, such as viscous hydrodynamic damping and operational factors like controller commands.

FOWTs experience greater loads than fixed systems due to significant rigid-body motion, which impacts its component's lifespans. For instance, a 10 MW rotor under surge and pitch motion shows increasing aerodynamic load with motion frequency, which reduces the components' durability (Bergua et al., 2022). Nejad et al. (2015), through numerical methods, observed up to a 200% increase in drivetrain fatigue in a 5 MW turbine compared to land-based setups.

Accurate modelling of floating-body hydrodynamics is critical, as

underestimations impact the ultimate and fatigue load states (ULS and FLS) (Robertson et al., 2017). Sensitivity analysis found that reducing hydrodynamic damping by 50% increases tower fatigue by 5%–10%, while similar reductions in structural damping led to 10%–20% increases (Espedal, 2016). Deviations of 20% in low-frequency surge motion alter the annual fatigue damage of copper umbilical cables by up to 13% (Land et al., 2023).

These findings underscore the substantial influence of damping on system response and the necessity to evaluate its effects on numerical predictions, as recommended by international standards, e.g. the analysis methodology for power cables in DNVGL-ST-0119 (2018). Key damping sources for standard FOWTs include structural damping, aerodynamic damping from rotor and wind-exposed surfaces, servo-dynamic-induced damping and hydrodynamic damping. Correctly estimating these sources is essential for accurately modelling the response of multi-physics systems like FOWTs.

This work concentrates on the study and determination of the

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hydrodynamic damping of a FOWT, a topic that remains under investigation by the international research community. Since 2011, numerous publications have referenced the calibration of FOWT hydrodynamic models against reduced-scale experimental tests (Nava et al., 2014, 2018; Robertson et al., 2017, 2020; Borg, 2018). In select instances, experimental measurements have been made publicly available (Robertson et al., 2020; Gueydon et al., 2021b; Robertson and Wang, 2021; Ransley et al., 2022; Robertson, 2023). Generally, most of these publications show good agreement between experiments and predicted system motion in the wave-frequency range, independent of the hydrodynamic model used (Robertson et al., 2017), even when wind actions are present (Azcona et al., 2019). Thus, the research community has refocused efforts on understanding the underpredictions observed at low frequencies (Robertson et al., 2017, 2020; Azcona et al., 2019).

In the extant literature, the most prevalent practice entails estimation of the diagonal terms of a 6×6 damping hydrodynamic matrix derived from decay tests. This approach, however, condenses the coupling between different degrees of freedom (DOFs) into a single coefficient. Consequently, it is not unexpected that when models calibrated with the properties derived from decay tests are used to analyse the operation under nonlinear waves loading, the results do not fully match, as any nonlinear system may exhibit different modal characteristics under different loading conditions (metocean and operation conditions in the case of an FOWT). However, Simos et al. (2018) found that applying similar hydrodynamic damping to the determined decays during computation of the quadratic transfer functions (QTFs) resulted in a reasonably good prediction of the response under irregular waves. The validity of those conclusions may be limited to the model and conditions tested (bichromatic waves with a component wave height of up to 6 m), as hydrodynamic damping it is known to be geometry and motion dependent.

Robertson et al. (2020) evaluated lumped hydrodynamic loads on a fixed semi-submersible model during forced oscillations (surge and pitch) and wave-only scenarios, comparing experimental data with numerical simulations from engineering fidelity models. The numerical models consistently underestimated the surge force and pitch moment, indicating that response underestimation in floating systems originates from the loading models rather than hydrodynamic damping. This underprediction was consistent across different hydrodynamic models and test types. Enhanced numerical accuracy was achieved through several adjustments: (1) accurately modelling experimental waves, particularly considering that laboratory wave spectra often deviate from target spectra, and emphasizing the need to understand the nature of undesired low-frequency waves; (2) incorporating QTFs into potential flow (PF) models; and (3) accounting for fully nonlinear wave fields in Morison element-based models, which improve the estimation of added-mass contributions. While wave stretching improved the surge estimates, it did not enhance the pitch predictions. Viscous drag proved significant but complex to model in irregular seas with varying amplitudes and frequencies. Although increased drag reduced load underestimation, it exacerbated response underestimation in floating configurations.

Wang et al. (2021) investigated difference-frequency wave loads on a fixed semi-submersible with a simplified geometry under bichromatic waves, comparing experimental results from a narrow wave basin (220×4 m) to computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and PF simulations. Uncertainties, including wave reflection effects, were incorporated into the total uncertainty rather than adjusting the wave elevation. Despite refined post-processing, their PF-based simulations significantly underestimated the surge wave loads, while the pitch results reached accuracy comparable to some CFD outcomes in specific conditions. The PF simulations showed a 20%–40% underestimation of normalised pitch moment and a severe reduction (1–2 orders) in surge force. These findings highlight the absence of viscous drag excitation in PF solutions, identified as a key factor in difference-frequency surge force at resonance. Their CFD predictions better matched the experimental

measurements, particularly at pitch resonance frequency. However, at surge resonance, discrepancies emerged, with numerical variability linked to wave height. Lower wave heights produced better alignment, attributed to reduced viscous drag and mesh resolution demands.

Wang et al. (2021) considered a symmetry condition at the x - z centre plane and at a lateral wall, which simplified their simulations at the cost of omitting finite basin reflection effects. This approach neglected antisymmetric fluid surface modes and the impact of floater-radiated and diffracted wave reflections on the longitudinal wave velocity field. Consequently, the modelled wave field lacked full fidelity; suggested improvements included a no-slip boundary condition for the lateral wall.

To address the numerical underestimation of low-frequency motion, researchers have proposed a range of methodologies. Simos et al. (2018) used QTFs and Newman approximation to investigate the impact of linearised damping on FOWT slow-drift response under only bichromatic and white noise wave conditions. Their study revealed that decoupling the system's DOFs in the QTFs led to improved predictions of surge motion. This simplification was also employed by Carmo et al. (2024). Focusing on second-order surge response amplitude operator (RAO) and damping, they found that the highest linearised damping ratios found in decay tests (10%–15%) showed the best fit with experimental results (Fig. 1).

Li and Bachynski-Polić (2021) used CFD simulations of a restrained FOWT to modify and calibrate hydrodynamic coefficients, such as the added mass, radiation damping and QTF contours, initially calculated using PF theory. This method, proposed by Robertson et al. (2020), involved increasing the added-mass and radiation damping coefficients by up to 10% at wave- and low-frequency ranges. These changes marginally affected the natural frequency predictions, maintaining deviations within 5%. Both their CFD and modified engineering-level models underestimated surge damping by approximately 50% compared to the decay test experiments, while slightly overestimating heave damping at low amplitudes.

PF-calculated QTFs underestimate second-order response at resonance periods, necessitating adjustments that notably impact wave-frequency regions. Incorporating surge experimental decay damping values worsen mismatches, as shown by Robertson et al. (2020). Updated PF models based on high-fidelity hydrodynamic simulations produce larger responses than experiments, which can be mitigated via further damping adjustments. Ultimately, Li and Bachynski-Polić (2021) achieved improved experimental agreement and more accurate estimates of damage-equivalent loads at mooring line fairleads, which were dominated by nonlinear wave loading.

Fig. 1. Second-order surge RAO obtained from bichromatic wave tests and numerical estimations considering different linearised damping levels on the calculation of full QTFs using the WAMIT software (Simos et al., 2018).

Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019) adopted a method that includes surge and pitch response energy by tuning viscous damping parameters to minimize the standard deviation between the predicted and observed system response. While this approach produced improved statistical values, significant underestimation of the pitch spectrum persisted, with the mean drift notably underestimated for wave heights exceeding 4 m. They also conducted operational modal analyses (OMA) of experimental responses from the most energetic sea states, which revealed an unusually high surge damping ratio ζ_1 (Fig. 2). This resulted either from spurious modes identified by the algorithm or significant damping contributions from the catenary mooring lines. The increasing significant wave height, H_s , in Fig. 2 is associated with a pink-noise spectrum containing energy from 4.5 to 18.2 s (H_s of 2.0 and 4.0 m), and a Pierson–Moskowitz spectrum with a peak period, T_p , of 12.4 and 15.0 s, corresponding to a H_s of 7.7 and 10.9 m, respectively. These authors attribute this to the adequacy of the OMA methods used and the violation of the linearity assumptions under which they were developed, potentially justifying the observed large damping.

Building on prior research and high-fidelity fluid behaviour visualizations (Robertson et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021, Wang et al., 2022a), Wang et al. (2022b) significantly improved low-frequency surge and pitch predictions using a hybrid hydrodynamic model. They extended beyond conventional calibration practices by introducing and validating two modifications to the axial drag force, $f_{D,Axial}$, in the traditional Morison equation (Eq. (1)):

$$f_{D,Axial} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot C_{D,Axial} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot |v_{R,n}| \cdot v_{R,n} \quad (1)$$

where $C_{D,Axial}$, ρ and A denote the axial drag coefficient, fluid density and reference area, respectively. Focusing on the axial direction of semi-submersible columns (heave plates), the first modification excluded drag loads from the negative relative velocity, $v_{R,n}$, doubling the fractional term to reflect drag loads consistent with traditional formulations at the heave plate's top and bottom (Eq. (2)):

$$f_{D,Axial} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_{D,Axial} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot |v_{R,n}| \cdot \max(v_{R,n}, 0) \quad (2)$$

This new formulation accounts for flow separation effects and retains physical relevance, converging to the traditional equation as the heave plate thickness approaches zero.

To incorporate frequency-dependent drag coefficients, Wang et al. (2021) applied a high-pass filter to the relative velocity and introduced a scaling factor, α (Eq. (3)):

$$f_{D,Axial} = \alpha \cdot f_{D,Axial,0} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot f_{D,Axial,f} \quad (3)$$

In this formulation, $f_{D,Axial,0}$ corresponds to Eq. (2), while the filtered drag component, $f_{D,Axial,f}$ (Eq. (4)), is determined using the filtered relative velocity, $\tilde{v}_{R,n}$:

$$f_{D,Axial,f} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot C_{D,Axial} \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot |\tilde{v}_{R,n}| \cdot \max(\tilde{v}_{R,n}, 0) \quad (4)$$

These two modifications represent an extension of the traditional Morison theory. Although the numerical hydrodynamic model became more complex, it improved low-frequency predictions and resolved the issue of conflicting axial drag coefficients for matching heave and pitch.

Laboratories offer ideal conditions for testing scaled models, but wave basins often exhibit inhomogeneities in the generated wave fields, as demonstrated by Lafleche et al. (2023). The finite size of wave tanks can hinder the replication of free-field conditions found in open seas, affecting model dynamics under specific metocean conditions. Resonance effects, not exclusive to enclosed basins, were observed by Costas et al. (2022) in A Coruña port, where resonant modes caused mooring line failures for vessels moored along jetties installed at different locations inside the port.

Testing in high-energy sea states is critical for evaluating ULSS, but these conditions also exacerbate wave reflections and might introduce spurious excitations from fluid free-surface modes. Numerical hydrodynamic models, employing first- and second-order PF solutions, assume free-field (or open-sea) conditions, and thus do not account for basin-geometry-dependent free-surface modes, an issue not mitigated by only considering experimental wave data in simulations.

In contrast, commercial wind farms lack the precision and comprehensiveness of laboratory measurements, relying on monitoring systems like buoys and lidar with limited accuracy. Measuring certain parameters, such as hydrodynamic load, is often infeasible or cost prohibitive for every turbine in a farm. Consequently, unknown environmental excitations reduce the applicability of mathematical techniques for determining FOWT dynamic characteristics, necessitating the use of OMA methods or output-only approaches for modal property identification.

As previously referenced, the exploitation of decay tests data represents the most widely used practice to estimate hydrodynamic damping (Borg, 2018; Robertson et al., 2020; Gueydon et al., 2021a). In the open sea, a free decay event (situation) may arise as a consequence of an emergency shutdown, as documented by Cermelli et al. (2018) for the 2 MW WindFloat prototype. However, such an event is considered an

Fig. 2. Damping ratio (ζ) for different sea states, estimated with OMA and calibrated values to provide an improved agreement of numerical response (measured via the standard deviation) with experiments (Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose, 2019).

anomaly (van Vondelen et al., 2022) and it occurs without control over the event characteristics and under the presence of concurrent unknown metocean conditions. Consequently, determination of the dynamic characteristics of the system under unknown operating conditions becomes paramount.

The majority of publications concerning FOWTs and system identification methods employ the time-domain logarithmic decrement (LogDec) method or its nonlinear version (PQ method) to identify the viscous hydrodynamic damping contribution from experiments or CFD simulations of decay tests. However, these methods are limited in their capabilities as they do not provide information about the system's mode shapes. The frequency-domain decomposition (FDD) and enhanced FDD methods have been employed to analyse the simulated response of spar-type FOWTs (Ruzzo et al., 2016, 2017), where the minimum signal length is studied to determine robust damping results; the aforementioned studies recommended 120 as the factor between the signal length and the longest period of the system. These studies also found that the FDD method did not provide the expected estimates when the JONSWAP wave peak period was close to the system's resonant frequency. Building upon this, Pimenta et al. (2020) utilised numerical simulations to check the applicability of the covariance-driven stochastic subspace identification (cov-SSI) algorithm in a controlled environment considering JONSWAP type spectrum waves of 6.0 m and 10.0 s, where the input signals were free of noise and clean stability diagrams were obtained.

The cov-SSI method was first applied to laboratory measurements of a scaled FOWT by Nava et al. (2018), who successfully identified heave and pitch resonance frequencies using white noise wave tests at a 1/36 scale, though damping estimation failed due to suboptimal tuning. Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019) employed the Ibrahim time-domain (ITD) method with wave tests considering pink noise and Pierson–Moskowitz type spectra for a 10 MW FOWT with a catenary mooring system, effectively determining modal properties across different sea states. However, in severe sea states with a narrow wave spectrum, the OMA-estimated damping values failed to align with those required by the second-order hydrodynamic model (Fig. 2). Notably, the system mass and stiffness matrices were not updated based on the determined mode shapes, and instead they were forced to rely on numerically derived properties.

Finally, output-only methods tested in the open sea, in fully free-field conditions but with uncontrolled environmental actions, have been conducted. The LogDec method was employed on an intermediate-scale spar to determine the damping from controlled decays (Ruzzo et al., 2018). Ruzzo et al. (2019) studied heave and yaw motion records of the same prototype to determine the modal damping and roll–yaw and pitch–yaw coupled terms. Kim et al. (2019) developed a structural health monitoring (SHM) system to detect damage on blades and towers of an FOWT. The SHM was validated by numerical simulations. More recently, Pimenta et al. (2024) studied the modal characteristics of a fully operative, full-scale (FS) wind turbine with a time-varying ballast system. Their study's primary focus was on the rigid-body modes of the floater and the flexible modes of the tower, with particular attention given to the dependency of the tower modes and the coupled floater dynamics. Their study extended to operational cases with the FOWT producing energy, and thus, with the rotor spinning. The authors then created a Campbell diagram, which mapped the operating FOWT's dynamic behaviour. To date, no publications that apply OMA methods to open-sea measurements of an FOWT have validated the identified modal properties by replicating the load cases numerically.

This study examines the dynamic characteristics of a 10 MW FOWT using experimental decay and JONSWAP irregular wave tests. The laboratory model employs an aerial taut-type station-keeping system (SKS) to reduce uncertainty by avoiding hydrodynamic loading on mooring lines, addressing limitations observed with the catenary SKS design used by Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019). Time-domain, output-only identification methods are applied to determine the 6×6 hydrodynamic damping matrix and explore cross-coupling effects among the system's

DOFs. Relationships between damping estimated from decay tests and irregular waves are also investigated. Efforts are also made to connect damping estimated via OMA methods with that required to compute second-order wave loading accurately, building on the efforts of Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019).

Persistent underestimation of low-frequency surge and pitch load and response, even with CFD models, highlights a critical issue, as no higher-fidelity solutions are available to address these engineering challenges. Consequently, this research also focuses on free-field conditions during wave basin experiments, hypothesizing that wave over-excitation in the basin, absent in simulations, could explain the observed underestimation trend seen in hydrodynamic loading. To address this, a mode-tracking algorithm is implemented to detect deviations in the system's dynamic properties and to identify stable modes of the basin's fluid free surface.

The following section provides an overview of hydrodynamic modelling of a floating body, fundamental principles of OMA and the automated mode tracking capabilities used in this study. Section 3 describes the case study, including the FS experimental FOWT and the tests conducted. Section 4 presents the results of the identification processes applied to decay and irregular wave tests. A discussion follows, analysing how basin free-surface modes influence the system's dynamics across the tested sea states. Finally, the conclusions drawn from this work are summarized in Section 5.

2. FOWT hydrodynamics and OMA methods

This section is devoted to recalling the equations of motion (EOMs) of a floating body subjected to wave loading. This is followed by a concise overview of the most pertinent capabilities of the OMA methods that are utilised in this study.

2.1. Equations of motion of a floating body

The EOMs of a system are generally expressed as in Eq. (5):

$$\mathbf{M} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{C} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{K} represent the system's total mass, damping and stiffness matrices, respectively, while vector \mathbf{f} comprises the external loading components. A moored floating body presents surge to yaw rigid-body DOFs (\mathbf{x} -vector components). Thus, the vectors have a dimension of six and the matrices contain 36 elements.

Considering that a moored floating body oscillates in a fluid, the general form of the EOMs of the system is transformed to account for the radiation problem, represented by the Cummins equation (Eq. (6)):

$$(\mathbf{M}_S + \mathbf{A}_\infty) \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \int_{-\infty}^t \mathbf{B}(t-\tau) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{x}}(\tau) \cdot d\tau + \mathbf{C}_{Add} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) + (\mathbf{K}_{Hs} + \mathbf{K}_{SKS}) \cdot \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{f} \quad (6)$$

where matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} represent the fluid added mass influenced by the body oscillations and the radiation damping due to the waves generated by the oscillating body, respectively. \mathbf{M}_S refers to the mass matrix of the floating structure and \mathbf{A}_∞ represents the body dragged fluid mass when its oscillation frequency tends to infinite. The linearised stiffness matrices, \mathbf{K}_{Hs} and \mathbf{K}_{SKS} , are defined as hydrostatic restoring terms and the SKS-provided stiffness, respectively. In Eq. (6), an additional damping term, \mathbf{C}_{Add} , has been included in the traditional expression of the Cummins equation, to account for additional energy dissipation mechanisms of the full system (i.e. the floating body and the SKS). Depending on the body geometry and the SKS design, matrices \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{K}_{Hs} and \mathbf{K}_{SKS} generally present off-diagonal elements. These terms are indicative of a certain level of coupling between these DOFs.

The EOMs in the frequency domain are given by Eq. (7):

$$[-\omega^2 \cdot (\mathbf{M}_S + \mathbf{A}(\omega)) + i \cdot \omega \cdot (\mathbf{B}(\omega) + \mathbf{C}_{add}) + (\mathbf{K}_{Hs} + \mathbf{K}_{SKS})] \cdot \mathbf{x}(\omega) = \mathbf{f}(\omega) \quad (7)$$

In this equation, matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} and the force vector, \mathbf{f} , are frequency dependent.

The primary external excitations in FOWTs are of metocean origin, as outlined below, which include hydrodynamic (waves and/or currents) and aerodynamic (wind) loads. With regard to wave loading theory, waves induce loads (Eq. (8)), which are usually divided into first-to third-order terms (Faltinsen, 1990):

$$\mathbf{f}_{WV} \approx \mathbf{f}_{WV,1} + \mathbf{f}_{WV,2} + \mathbf{f}_{WV,3} \quad (8)$$

The linear wave loading is proportional to the wave elevation and represents the wave diffraction loads on the structure (Eq. (9)):

$$\mathbf{f}_{WV,1,j} = R \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^N A_k \cdot X_{k,j} \cdot e^{i \cdot \omega_k \cdot t} \right\} \quad j = 1, \dots, 6 \quad (9)$$

The second-order wave loading terms are derived from the interaction between waves of multiple lengths and the floating body. Commonly, these are modelled by the means of QTFs (Eq. (10)):

$$\mathbf{f}_{WV,2,j} = R \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^N A_k \cdot \bar{A}_l \cdot QTF_{klj}^- \cdot e^{i(\omega_k - \omega_l) \cdot t} + A_k \cdot A_l \cdot QTF_{klj}^+ \cdot e^{i(\omega_k + \omega_l) \cdot t} \right\} \quad j = 1, \dots, 6 \quad (10)$$

The developed loads depend on the product of the amplitude of the waves and the system response amplitude (A_k, A_l). The interaction between two frequencies leads to the development of difference-frequency (QTF^-) and sum-frequency (QTF^+) terms.

2.2. OMA methods

The dynamics of a fully operational FOWT present highly nonlinear, time-variant and nonstationary behaviour. The presence of harmonic excitations, induced by the rotation of the blades, complicates the discernment of structural modes and operational loads. Furthermore, the identification of modal properties is rendered even more challenging by operating the system under random turbulent wind and wave conditions, while actuating on nacelle yaw, blade pitch and/or other control systems.

In this study, we focus on decay and irregular wave tests of a non-deformable scale model (Section 3). It is acknowledged that the system under scrutiny does not fully embody a functional FOWT. The primary objective of the present investigation is to identify the characteristics of the low-frequency modes of the structure, i.e., the rigid-body modes of the scaled model. Furthermore, it is expected that the investigation will identify the free-surface modes of the fluid enclosed in the wave basin, and that these modes will be understood in terms of their interference with the system's response.

In the context of identifying the dynamic properties of a linear or a weakly nonlinear system, a range of output-only algorithms have been developed. The time-domain methods selected for this study encompass the classical LogDec method (both the linear and nonlinear versions, LogDec and PQ, respectively), and the more complex cov-SSI and the data-driven stochastic subspace identification (dat-SSI) methods. Frequency-domain identification methods have been disregarded due to the disadvantage that they introduce when working with systems where relevant modes are spread over a wide range of the spectrum, as is the case in this study. In such situation, the calculation of long correlation functions is imperative to enhance the low-frequency resolution of the spectrum and consequently attain reliable modal parameters. However, the use of these correlation functions can lead to the development of noise tails, which, in turn, can introduce further errors and spurious

poles into the identification process. Furthermore, Ruzzo et al. (2016) demonstrated that the FDD method encounters challenges when dealing with irregular waves that have peak periods close to the system's resonance period. Nevertheless, FDD methods have been employed, without reported problems, to identify the modal properties of FOWT components with higher natural frequencies (Kim et al., 2019). Drawing upon the authors' experience and knowledge, dat-SSI offers superior identification of FOWT rigid-body modes, albeit incurring greater computational cost compared to cov-SSI. Despite the fact these methods have been formulated on the basis of linear time-invariant systems that are subject to white-noise-type excitation, the use of SSI methods and their capacity to function with nonlinear systems under energetic sea states with narrow wave spectra is a subject of particular interest.

All the methods proposed in this study provide information regarding the fundamental frequencies and damping ratios of the system, but only SSI methods provide information about the shape of the system modes associated to each frequency. It is important to understand that the mode shapes detected by OMA methods correspond to the operational deflection shapes (ODSs). In contrast to mode shapes, ODSs are influenced by other modes, such as those introduced by an operational load. Consequently, they exhibit forced and resonant vibration components, while mode shapes only consider the resonant contribution.

The theoretical background of these OMA methods can be found in numerous publications (Van Overschee and De Moor, 1996; Ljung, 1999; Chauhan, 2016). The algorithms, as implemented in the EOMA software are described by Galván (2024). However, the system property identification process does not simply entail the application of an algorithm. Instead, SSI methodologies were designed to find a set of real and virtual/spurious poles from the correlation functions matrix (cov-SSI) or recorded data (dat-SSI) of a set of signals produced by a stochastic process. Then, a stability analysis of the detected poles is performed to discern between real and virtual poles. The analysis is contingent upon the satisfaction of a series of conditions by the newly identified poles, as the model order is increased. The stability of the estimated poles is determined by comparing them with precedent poles, allowing a maximum deviation of the following parameters: (1) damping frequency, (2) damping ratio and (3) the modal assurance criterion (MAC) function. Achieving level 4 stability is contingent upon fulfilling all conditions. Additionally, poles with negative damping ratios or with values larger than a threshold are discarded. The application of the stability analysis to LogDec or PQ methods entails classification of the identified cycles. It is evident that the conditions relative to the MAC function are not applied when using these methods, and the maximum level of stability (i.e., 4) is then achieved when conditions (1) and (2) above are simultaneously fulfilled. In this work, the simple LogDec method is employed to process the system's response to decay and irregular wave tests. Fig. 3 provides an example application of the LogDec method supported by the stability conditions described above. The level of stability of the detected cycles is indicated by the coloured markers at the end of each cycle. Note that only cycles with the highest stability level (green markers in Fig. 3) are considered when determining the mean damped period and damping ratio, which provide higher confidence in the estimations than if all detected cycles are considered.

Finally, in the SSI methods chosen for this study, some system-dependent criteria may be added to choose the most representative mode (i.e., ODS) and the associated frequency and damping ratio among the stable poles. The selection of the most representative pole is of key importance to capture the system's dynamics.

The OMA is typically executed with a substantial volume of data across multiple channels, enabling continuous monitoring of the system. Manual identification of the system's properties can be a laborious process; thus, automation of this process is imperative. Furthermore, automation of OMA processes is instrumental in the development of SHM applications and digital twins.

Fig. 3. Results of the LogDec method, showing the stability level of peaks and valleys based on modal property stability (left), evolution of the damped period (middle) and the damping ratio across the pitch cycles (right). Mean values are indicated by a green horizontal dashed line (note that negative damping ratio samples and unstable peaks/valleys are excluded from the calculation of the mean values).

During the generation of a stability diagram, the separation between real and virtual modes is partially done by means of user-defined limits; however, a method is needed to relate the estimates with the corresponding physical mode. The simplest (and not very correct) way to do this is to consider the highest-order state-space model estimations as the physical mode. However, this does not ensure that the best-fitting mode is estimated (Magalhães et al., 2009).

In EOMA, modal estimations from a stabilisation diagram can be automatically treated using three different approaches to select the representative modes: (a) maximum summation of MAC, (b) clustering of the stable poles and minimum distance function with respect to a reference mode and (c) minimum distance function. The first strategy is based on the mode indicator function sumMAC, which retains the ODS showing the largest summation of MAC along the columns of the auto-MAC matrix of the stable poles. The damping frequency and damping ratio inside the frequency band of interest are usually averaged to provide a mean value. The remaining two strategies are bit more complex, and they are supported by some knowledge of the system. These consider reference mode information that, in EOMA, it can be provided by the user or estimated from a set of initial analyses using the sumMAC approach.

As proposed by Magalhães et al. (2009), information from the stabilisation diagram can be directly interpreted by a cluster analysis. From this analysis, different groups of modes are generated, which should show large within-cluster homogeneity and inter-cluster heterogeneity. Clustering techniques can be non-hierarchical (K-means is a well-known algorithm) or hierarchical. Hierarchical clustering techniques are used by Magalhães et al. (2009) and Pimenta et al. (2020). In the frequency-damping 2D plane, clusters can be generated by means of the Euclidean distance between the two modes (data points), however, the distance function, d_{a-b} , employed by Pimenta et al. (2020) is used here (Eq. (11)):

$$d_{a-b} = \alpha \cdot \left| \frac{f_a - f_b}{f_b} \right| + \beta \cdot [1 - \text{MAC}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})]. \quad (11)$$

This is indeed a weighted version (through coefficients α and β) of the function defined by Magalhães et al. (2009), where f_a and f_b denote to the natural frequency detected by the identification algorithm and the reference frequency provided by the user, respectively.

The MAC is calculated using Eq. (12):

$$\text{MAC}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \frac{|\mathbf{a}^H \cdot \mathbf{b}|^2}{(\mathbf{a}^H \cdot \mathbf{a}) \cdot (\mathbf{b}^H \cdot \mathbf{b})} \quad (12)$$

where super-index H denotes the Hermitian (conjugate transpose) vector, which determines the degree of similarity between two mode shapes, \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , with unity indicating identical vectors.

A symmetric 2D matrix of dimensions $n_{\text{Modes.Stable}} \times n_{\text{Modes.Stable}}$ can then be built with the distances between the estimation of the two modes, the so-called distance matrix. The single-linkage methodology is used in the hierarchical tree construction. Once the hierarchical tree is built the tree cut level must be selected through a maximum distance value. Magalhães et al. (2009) recommend using the limits employed when generating the stabilisation diagrams. The modal parameters of the poles of the same cluster are then averaged and the MAC function of the averaged clusters' mode shapes and the reference mode shape is calculated. The cluster exhibiting the highest MAC is then selected as the solution.

To reduce the number of processes, an alternative methodology is proposed here, which removes the clustering process by directly computing a distance vector (instead of a matrix) according to Eq. (11). The modes involved are the stable poles estimated by the identification process and the reference modal parameters involved in calculating the distance. However, one drawback compared to previous strategies is that this approach does not provide statistics of the modal properties.

3. Description of the FOWT and the experimental setup

Data from tests dedicated to studying the hydrodynamic behaviour of the DeltaWind FOWT (Fig. 4) are employed in the case studies in this work. Publicly available measurements of the round-robin wind tests of MaRINET2 (Gueydon et al., 2021b; Judge et al., 2021; Gueydon et al., 2021b), recorded at the laboratories of the École Centrale de Nantes (ECN), are used to illustrate this work.

3.1. FOWT model properties at full scale

The reduced model studied at ECN (Fig. 4) represents the InnWind-10MW-178+DeltaWind FOWT at a scale of 1/60. The experimental model was constructed without a rotor and was made stiff enough to avoid the deformation of the system's components during the tests. Therefore, as stated by Judge et al. (2021), it can be assumed that the tower and hull are rigid. In order to mitigate the uncertainty associated with catenary mooring lines as much as possible, an aerial SKS was employed. The dimensions of the floating substructure are provided in Table 1. Further information regarding the system's components can be found in Judge et al. (2021).

For the FS ECN model indicated in Table 1, the system properties

Fig. 4. Reduced scale model of the DeltaWind FOWT at Ifremer facilities, France (Gueydon et al. (2021a)).

required to build the system's EOMs (Eq. (6)) are presented here. Properties are expressed in SI units (s, m, rad and kg) and the EOMs are calculated for the system's centre of mass (CM). The FS mass matrix of the six DOFs rigid-body model of the system (\mathbf{M} in Eq. (13)) includes the model's physical properties, \mathbf{M}_s , and the fluid added mass involved by the system oscillating at infinite frequency, \mathbf{A}_∞ . The total stiffness matrix, \mathbf{K} , of the horizontally positioned system at equilibrium position is given in Eq. (14) and results from the summation of the linearised hydrostatic \mathbf{K}_{Hs} and mooring stiffness $\mathbf{K}_{SKS}(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0})$ matrices. Equations (13) and (14) are:

$$\mathbf{M}_{CM} = 10^6 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 38.6 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -17.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 38.6 & 0 & 16.7 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 52.0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 18.9 & 0 & 41,086.8 & 0 & 0 \\ -18.3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 44,335.9 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -4.5 & 0 & 13,153.3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{CM} = 10^3 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 80.4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1,982.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 84.4 & 0 & -2,081.5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 5,051.2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -2,081.0 & 0 & 3,028,785.4 & 0 & 75,780.2 \\ 1,982.3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 3,042,273.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -501.2 & 0 & 1,001,477.7 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

To relate the damping values and relative damping ratios, the system's critical damping matrix, \mathbf{C}_c , must be calculated. For the ECN model, this matrix is referenced about the system's CM and its elements are estimated at equilibrium position, according to Eq. (15):

$$C_{c,ij} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{K_{ij} \cdot M_{ij}} \quad \forall \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 6, \quad (15)$$

where i denotes the damped DOFs and j describes the motion DOFs.

At this point, the information available is sufficient to determine the natural periods and mode shapes of the rigid-body modes of the FOWT numerically (Table 2). Due to the nearly constant stiffness of the model SKS, the influence of the system's excursions across the x - y plane on the natural periods is very low and can be disregarded. As expected for a

Table 1

Parameters defining the floating substructure geometry tested at ECN. Objective values and built-in model deviations are shown in grey.

Param. no. [-]	Description	Model scale	Full scale	Units
1	Distance between triangular layout vertices	1.1000	66.000 66.000 (+0.0%)	[m]
2	Columns height	0.6250	37.500 37.500 (+0.0%)	[m]
3	Outer diameter of columns	0.2420	14.520 14.500 (+0.1%)	[m]
4	Pontoons' height	0.1170	7.020 7.000 (+0.3%)	[m]
6	Pontoons' width	0.1810	10.860 10.875 (-0.1%)	[m]

semi-submersible-type floating structure, the natural periods can be split into low- and wave-frequency. It is evident that surge, sway and yaw are components of the first group, while the remaining DOFs are within or in close proximity to the first-order wave excitation frequency range.

3.2. Experimental tests analysed

The experiments were performed in the wave basin of ECN, which is 50.0 m long, 30.0 m wide and has a water depth of 5.0 m. The scaled model was placed 17.0 m away from the wave generator inside the basin. During the experimental campaign, decay tests, regular and irregular waves with and without wind loads tests were performed. Due to the short duration of the regular waves tests (about 500 s), the ratio between the duration of the test signals and the longest resonance period of the system (i.e., the surge, about to 150 s) is smaller than 4.0, which is a poor ratio. For example, recommendations in the literature often refer to 120 times the longest system period as being a suitable ratio (Ruzzo et al., 2017). The influence of this ratio on the standard deviation of the system's properties was estimated by Pimenta et al. (2020). We note that the measured properties from the experimental regular wave tests may suffer from large uncertainties, especially the low-frequency DOFs of the

semi-submersible. Thus, regular wave tests are not considered in this study. The processed signal duration of the irregular wave tests was 10, 500 s which returned a signal length to surge period ratio of 70, closer to a suitable value. A summary of the irregular waves' characteristics at model scale (MS) and FS, determined from 11 experimental tests, is provided in Table 3.

As indicated in Section 2, narrow energy spectrum excitation is not the ideal situation for the application of OMA methods. One might consider utilisation of experimental data from other publicly available campaigns in which irregular waves with a white noise spectrum were tested (Robertson, 2023). However, the dataset selected represents more realistic ocean conditions, and more importantly, the system's response is influenced by basin free-surface modes. Clear visualisation of the extra, basin-introduced energy may support the hypothesis that a lack of

Table 2

Numerically determined natural frequencies, periods and mode shape components of the undamped FOWT system at equilibrium position. Units considered: meters and radians.

Mode no. [-]	DOF	Frequency [Hz]	Period [s]	Modeshape components [-]					
				Surge	Sway	Heave	Roll	Pitch	Yaw
1	Surge	0.0066	151.15	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	Sway	0.0066	151.17	0.0	-1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3	Heave	0.0493	20.28	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4	Roll	0.0410	24.42	0.0	-0.7	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0
5	Pitch	0.0394	25.38	-0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.6	0.0
6	Yaw	0.0135	74.32	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0

Table 3

Objective characteristics of the irregular waves and the associated water depth of the tests held at ECN.

LC Id.	Water level	Waves							
		Spectrum		Direction	Shape coeff.	Model scale		Full scale	
		$S(\omega)$	ϕ_{Wv}			Significant height	Peak period	Significant height	Peak period
				D_{MS}	γ				
-	[m]	-	[deg]	[-]	[m]	[s]	[m]	[s]	
154	5.000	JONSWAP	180.0	3.300	0.050	1.290	3.00	9.99	
155	5.000	JONSWAP	180.0	3.300	0.075	1.290	4.50	9.99	
156	5.000	JONSWAP	180.0	3.300	0.100	1.807	6.00	14.02	
157	5.000	JONSWAP	180.0	3.300	0.100	2.580	6.00	19.98	
158–162	5.000	JONSWAP	180.0	3.300	0.150	1.807	9.00	14.00	
163	5.000	JONSWAP	180.0	3.300	0.150	2.582	9.00	19.98	
164	5.000	JONSWAP	180.0	3.300	0.200	2.582	12.00	19.98	

hydrodynamic excitation is the cause of the underprediction of surge and pitch loads reported in the literature.

3.3. Experimental data available

As expressed by Brincker and Ventura (2015), identification of the modal properties of a system involves the process of correlating the dynamic characteristics of a mathematical model with the physical properties of the system derived from experimental measurements. Hence, data acquisition from tests that are held in a controlled environment is critical to identify the dynamic characteristics of the system.

At ECN’s facilities, the laboratory model was fitted with reflectors for a Qualysis-type system, whose indirect measurements are obtained with respect to the basin floor. Three uniaxial load cells were also installed to record the tension in the mooring lines. Additionally, a set of five wave gauges measured the wave elevation at separate locations. The raw experimental measurements present, at FS, a sampling frequency of 12.91 Hz.

4. Identification of the FOWT’s properties

In this section, the FS modal characteristics of the FOWT determined from its rigid-body response recorded during the reduced scale experiments are presented.

4.1. Decay tests

In this study, experimental free decay tests are utilised to ascertain the natural resonance period and the modal damping of the FOWT’s rigid-body DOFs. The LogDec time-domain method and its nonlinear version, PQ, are utilised to characterise hydrodynamic damping. Given the absence of damping introduced by the SKS due to its aerial configuration and line material, it is hypothesised that the observed damping is of hydrodynamic origin. However, if the SKS does indeed introduce damping, the analysis and comparison of the modal properties determined from the free-floating and moored system decay can support estimation of the damping introduced by the SKS, as was previously

done (Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose, 2019). However, it should be noted that the SKS damping estimation obtained from free decays may significantly differ from the damping of the mooring lines subjected to wave loading. Therefore, SKS damping may remain an unknown and a source of uncertainty as pointed by Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019). The rationale behind the selection of the present experimental campaign pertains to the employment of an aerial SKS configuration, a design that serves to mitigate the uncertainty associated with this sub-system of the FOWT’s structure.

In the following section, nonlinear hydrodynamic damping is studied and the influence of the cross-coupled DOFs is investigated (Section 4.1.1). Next, the mean damped frequencies and damping ratios are determined (Section 4.1.2). This section concludes with the determination of the full 6×6 hydrodynamic damping matrix of the FOWT (Section 4.1.3).

4.1.1. Nonlinear hydrodynamic damping

This section is devoted to investigating the relationship of individual hydrodynamic damping ratios determined from decay with the velocity of the system during each cycle. These results are presented in Figs. 5–8, which are explained in detail below.

These figures refer to the DOFs of rigid-body motion (note that for simplicity, the sway and roll DOFs have been omitted). System modes with separate natural periods showing poor coupling have been removed for clarity. Each figure (e.g., Fig. 5) contains two types of plots. For example, in Fig. 5(a), the damping ratio of the i th DOF, ζ_i , as determined from the decay tests performed to study the j th DOF (surge to yaw), is illustrated as a scatter plot as a function of the mean velocity with sign, \bar{v}_i , of the i th DOF across a cycle of duration T_i . In Fig. 5(b), the contours of ζ_i are presented as a function of \bar{v}_i and the signed mean velocity of the $j \neq i$ (\bar{v}_j) DOF. In the study of ζ_i , the signed mean velocities \bar{v}_i and \bar{v}_j across a single cycle of the i th DOF have been determined as per Eq. (16), where x denotes the displacement or rotation measured during the test:

Fig. 5. Surge relative damping ratio ζ_1 . a) Velocity to damping ratio relationship for surge DOF during different decays tests (from surge to yaw: ●, ●, ●, ●, ● and, ●; ● and x indicating peaks and valleys, respectively) and b) contours as function of surge and yaw DOFs' signed mean velocity.

$$\bar{v}_i = \text{sign}(x_i(1) - x_i(0)) \cdot \frac{1}{T_i} \sum_{n=0}^{T_i/\Delta t} |x_i(n+1) - x_i(n)|, \quad (16)$$

$$\bar{v}_j = \text{sign}(x_j(1) - x_j(0)) \cdot \frac{1}{T_j} \sum_{n=0}^{T_j/\Delta t} |x_j(n+1) - x_j(n)|.$$

Generation of the plots was achieved by utilising the stable modal parameters (level 4, see Section 2.2) that were ascertained through an identification analysis by employing the LogDec method, which encompassed all the peaks and valleys present in the experimental decay signals. However, due to the significant dispersion of the damping at low velocity amplitudes, it was necessary to remove some of the samples in order to eliminate outliers and create a clearer contour plot. This phenomenon of dispersion has also been observed by Li and Bachynski-Polić (2021), who attribute it to background mechanical friction generated during the experiments.

It should be noted that the contour plots provide graphical means to determine the 6×6 matrix of the system (determined in Section 4.1.3 using a different methodology). The interpolated values along the abscissa axis ($y = 0$, no motion of the secondary DOF) represent the damping ratios of the diagonal of the 6×6 matrix. Therefore, the variation across the vertical $\Delta\zeta_i(\bar{v}_i = \text{constant})$ represents the damping

contribution of the secondary j th DOF (or coupled DOF, if its influence on ζ_i is observed) to the primary i th DOF damping ratio, and thus, the ζ_{ij} component. This is true while the remaining DOFs present a low response, and thus, under the assumption that the influence of these DOFs is negligible relative to the main DOF response.

Surge exhibits a nearly linear increase in damping with velocity, although some curvature in the relationship becomes evident at higher velocities (Fig. 5(a)). In contrast, heave damping demonstrates a distinctly nonlinear behaviour (Fig. 6(a)). The damping ratio of pitch motion remains relatively constant, typically near or below 1%, with a slight increase observed for velocities greater than 0.25 deg/s (Fig. 7 (b)). For yaw, the damping shows a linear dependence on the rotational velocity (Fig. 8(b)). No significant differences are observed between the damping associated with peaks or valleys at similar velocity amplitudes. This suggests that, for the tested model, the direction of motion does not notably affect the damping characteristics.

When examining the influence of secondary DOFs on damping, it should be noted that the sample size is limited, particularly in the region of interest where primary and secondary DOFs are expected to exhibit similar velocities. Surge is particularly affected by poor data density due to its long natural period. However, there is some indication that the yaw DOF exerts an influence on surge damping ratio. In the case of

Fig. 6. Heave relative damping ratio ζ_3 . a) Velocity to damping ratio relationship for heave DOF during different decays tests (from surge to yaw: ●, ●, ●, ●, ● and, ●; ● and x indicating peaks and valleys, respectively) and b) contours as function of heave and pitch DOFs' signed mean velocity.

Fig. 7. Pitch relative damping ratio ζ_5 . a) Contours as function of pitch and heave DOFs' signed mean velocity and b) velocity to damping ratio relationship for pitch DOF during different decays tests (from surge to yaw: \bullet , \circ , \cdot , \times , \circ , \times and \bullet , \circ and \times indicating peaks and valleys, respectively).

Fig. 8. Yaw relative damping ratio ζ_6 . a) Contours as function of yaw and surge DOFs' signed mean velocity and b) velocity to damping ratio relationship for yaw DOF during different decays tests (from surge to yaw: \bullet , \circ , \cdot , \times , \circ , \times and \bullet , \circ and \times indicating peaks and valleys, respectively).

heave, the largest damping ratios are observed when significant simultaneous pitch velocities are present (Fig. 6(b)). The data points exhibit an X-shaped pattern, clearly linking heave and pitch velocity to damping. Pitch damping is strongly influenced by heave, as the damping ratio gradients along the vertical axis show in Fig. 7(a). The observed trend suggests that an increase in heave velocity leads to an increase in pitch damping. The slight influence of secondary DOFs on yaw damping can be inferred from Fig. 8(a), where the data points again form X-shaped patterns, indicative of a relationship between surge and yaw velocities.

To enhance the robustness of the findings and populate the contours with a more representative set of data points, it would be beneficial to increase the number of decay tests in future experimental campaigns. These tests should be designed to introduce initial offsets in pairs of DOFs, thereby exciting two DOFs simultaneously. In the physical models or prototypes, unexpected cross couplings may emerge due to inaccuracies in construction and/or installation (e.g., surge–sway couplings resulting from SKS deployment, among others). Consequently, it may be advantageous to investigate all the potential couplings when analysing real systems.

4.1.2. Linearisation of the hydrodynamic damping

Statistics of the system's damped periods, T_d , and linearised damping ratios, ζ , (when available) were determined using the LogDec and PQ identification methods, as illustrated in Fig. 9. Furthermore, the results presented by Gueydon et al. (2021a) for surge, heave and pitch DOFs are also included (as reference results). Although the damping observed in the previous section was nonlinear, the modal characteristics are linearised. The linear damping values that are input to the frequency-domain solvers based on PF are responsible for determining the hydrodynamic coefficients of a floating system.

The damped periods presented here are in very good agreement with reference results (Gueydon et al., 2021b). It is observed that the periods demonstrate minimal deviation when different lengths of the decay signals are processed. Conversely, the damping ratios demonstrate a discernible reliance on the number of peaks utilised in the analysis, as anticipated. The most significant disparities (up to -83.8%) are evident in the heave DOF when all the peaks (indicated by -1 , as illustrated in Fig. 9) are processed. It is noteworthy that these discrepancies are indicative of a greater nonlinear damping contribution. In this study, the damping characteristics provided by Gueydon et al. (2021a) were linearised, by considering different numbers of peaks or even peaks and/or

Fig. 9. Mean damped periods (T_d) and damping ratios (ζ) of the six rigid-body DOFs of the FOWT. Red lines indicate the standard deviation ($\pm \sigma$). Inside the parentheses, the first peak/valley and the total number of peaks/valleys involved in the calculation are given (-1 indicates that all peaks/valleys are considered). “Ref.” indicates the results adapted from Gueydon et al. (2021a), in which only surge, heave and pitch results are available.

valleys in the calculation of the damping ratios, as this information was not available. Reasonably good agreement is found between the literature results and those obtained with our PQ method (see Fig. 9, where the analysis is performed considering the first to the third peaks and valleys, indicated as 1/3 in the legend).

4.1.3. Determination of the full 6×6 damping matrix

Up to this point, the determined hydrodynamic damping has corre-

sponded to the diagonal terms of the 6×6 matrix. Nonetheless, given the stiffness provided by the SKS, the physical characteristics of the system and the shape of the floater, couplings between the system’s DOFs exist. The off-diagonal damping terms are calculated as (Eq. (17)):

$$C_{ij} = 2 \cdot \zeta_{ij} \cdot \sqrt{K_{ij} \cdot M_{ij}}. \tag{17}$$

Ruzzo et al. (2019) used the half-power frequency-domain method to determine the cross terms by analysing the second dominant peak of the

Fig. 10. Pitch experimental signal recorded during the surge decay tests. Shown are unfiltered and band-pass-filtered signals with central frequencies at the surge and pitch natural frequencies.

system response spectrum. To work with multifrequency decay signals in the time domain, the empirical mode decomposition (EMD) technique could be used here. The decomposition process of the EMD is based on the signal maxima/minima to extract intrinsic mode functions containing frequency and damping information. EMD does not rely on traditional filtering processes, and thus avoids their limitations. Despite the possible advantages of the EMD over simpler methods, the proposed methodology still uses the LogDec method, which is preferred due to its widespread use.

The proposed methodology (Fig. 10) is predicated on the use of DOF-specific band-pass filters to recondition the time response input to the LogDec algorithm. To identify a set of signals automatically, analysis of the LogDec-detected mode stability (Section 2.1) yields robust results. The central frequencies and bandwidth of the fifth-order Butterworth filter employed for each DOF are presented in Table 4.

As illustrated in Fig. 10, it is possible to determine two distinct mode components (and modal properties) from the pitch response, each occurring at a different frequency. Subsequently, for each test and each DOF signal, six distinct identification processes are executed, corresponding to the six different band-filtered signals obtained from each DOF (36 processes for each test and identification method setup). However, the resulting expanded identification algorithm may not be suitable for systems where coupled DOFs are closely spaced in frequency, as the filters may subtract significant energy from the corresponding modes. In such scenarios, the EMD or a frequency-domain identification method is more appropriate.

The full system damping matrix C (which considers the mass and stiffness matrices provided in Section 3) is presented in Eq. (18) (given in S.I. units):

$$C = 10^3 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 86.2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -386.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 49.6 & 0 & -298.6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 481.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -412.6 & 0 & 178.732 & 0 & 0 \\ -387.1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 150,246.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 12,289.7 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

It is evident that the matrix is not fully symmetric, although cross terms are close. In order to achieve this degree of symmetry, identification of the band-filtered signals of the cross terms has been performed by neglecting the first peak (initial surge peak in Fig. 10), thereby removing some nonlinearity. This meticulous approach is underpinned by the observation that the coupling level of surge–pitch was found to be higher in the pitch response ($C_{5,1}$) in comparison to the surge response ($C_{1,5}$), and a symmetric damping matrix was forced.

4.2. Parked FOWT under JONSWAP spectrum irregular wave tests

In the tests investigated in this section, the FOWT was moored and subjected to irregular waves characterised by a JONSWAP spectrum and a target shape coefficient of 3.3. Including repetitions, up to 11 experimental tests of this type are available. The seven different significant wave heights and peak period pairs tested are summarized in Table 3. It is important to note that all the tests involving waves consider a heading

Table 4
Frequency lines and bandwidths considered in the identification processes.

Frequency line no.	DOF	Frequency	Period	Bandwidth	
		[Hz]	[s]	[Hz]	[s]
1	Surge	0.0066	152.35	$0.431 \cdot 10^{-3}$	10.00
2	Sway	0.0066	151.95	$0.434 \cdot 10^{-3}$	10.00
3	Heave	0.0479	20.89	$6.910 \cdot 10^{-3}$	3.00
4	Roll	0.0391	25.59	$7.710 \cdot 10^{-3}$	5.00
5	Pitch	0.0380	26.31	$7.288 \cdot 10^{-3}$	5.00
6	Yaw	0.0141	70.85	$2.002 \cdot 10^{-3}$	10.00

Fig. 11. PSD of the irregular wave (FS) elevation, ξ , at the model location recorded at ECN without the model installed. All publicly available wave calibration tests consider a wave peak period of 14.0 s.

of 180°, and thus, the excitation of sway, roll and yaw may be poor, and, theoretically, only induced by the static offsets found during the analysis of the FOWT’s equilibrium state. Consequently, the identification of these modes presents a challenge. However, tests with oblique waves should help identify all the rigid-body modes simultaneously (Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose, 2019; Pimenta et al., 2020).

The power spectrum density (PSD) functions of the undisturbed wave elevation recorded during the calibration of the experimental waves from Gueydon et al. (2021b) are presented in Fig. 11. Only five measurements of the 9.0 m and 14.0 s irregular waves without the scaled model inside are publicly available. It is important to note that these are shorter than the experimental records with the model installed, and thus, the frequency content of the undisturbed waves may be different to that illustrated in Fig. 11. To visualise the period range that waves excite and identify possible interactions, the FOWT’s and the wave basin’s free-surface resonant periods are included. Fig. 11 reveals that the system’s natural periods in the wave-frequency range (heave, roll and pitch) may interfere with the basin’s free-surface modes $T_{Basin,(2,3)}$ and $T_{Basin,(3,2)}$. Some unexpected energy also developed around 50.0 and 115.0 s, which reveals excitation of the free-surface modes at periods $T_{Basin,(0,1)}$ or $T_{Basin,(1,1)}$ and $T_{Basin,(1,0)}$, respectively. Further information of the basin’s free-surface modes is given in Section 4.2.3.

In studying a semi-submersible FOWT under irregular waves, second-order excitations may arise. Table 5 outlines the difference- and sum-periods that could theoretically occur during the experiments, based on the energy levels of the studied sea state. Note that the resulting periods relate the natural periods of the system, $1/f_i$, and the peak period, $1/f_p$, of the irregular waves.

Following a detailed description of the experimental tests, the setup of the OMA methods, identification process results and analysis of spurious excitation during the experiments are discussed in the following sections.

4.2.1. Setup of the OMA methods

The configuration of the identification methods utilised in this study is outlined briefly below. This subsection provides a detailed description of the setup characteristics of the OMA methods, as well as the sensitivity of the cov-SSI and dat-SSI methods to various parameters.

The stability criteria employed during the identification processes are based on a maximum deviation of 5% for the natural frequency, damping ratio and MAC function between contiguous modes. For the LogDec and PQ methods, this limit has been increased to 15% and 80%, respectively. Additionally, poles exhibiting negative damping ratios or damping ratios exceeding 50% are excluded from the mode selection and property extraction steps.

To assess the robustness of the identification methods, their configurations and the mode selection techniques tested, a notably high

Table 5
Periods of interest due to nonlinear irregular waves in the experiments at ECN.

Wave peak period, T_p		10.0 s		14.0 s		20.0 s		Units
Frequency line no.	DOF	$\frac{1}{(f_p - f_i)}$	$\frac{1}{(f_p + f_i)}$	$\frac{1}{(f_p - f_i)}$	$\frac{1}{(f_p + f_i)}$	$\frac{1}{(f_p - f_i)}$	$\frac{1}{(f_p + f_i)}$	
1	Surge	10.7	9.4	15.4	12.8	23.0	17.7	[s]
2	Sway	10.7	9.4	15.4	12.8	23.0	17.7	[s]
3	Heave	19.2	6.8	42.5	8.4	470.5	10.2	[s]
4	Roll	16.4	7.2	30.9	9.0	91.6	11.2	[s]
5	Pitch	16.1	7.2	29.9	9.1	83.4	11.4	[s]
6	Yaw	11.6	8.8	17.4	11.7	27.9	15.6	[s]

maximum damping ratio has been adopted. This elevated threshold was deliberately set to allow the algorithm to identify exceptionally high damping values. Such a setup aims to prevent the exclusion of large damping needs of certain DOFs reported by Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019) to fit the numerical response of the system accurately when subjected to irregular wave conditions.

Among the numerous parameters available for configuring the identification methods implemented in EOMA, this study examines the influence of the signal sampling frequency, the number of blocks used in

the SSI methods and the automatic mode selection algorithm on the response of the identified system.

An analysis of the signal sampling frequency was conducted to evaluate its effect on the population of stable poles determined by the cov-SSI method for a fixed number of blocks (eight). Particular attention was given to the number of modes detected in the lowest frequency range corresponding to the surge DOF. This mode, which exhibits the system's longest natural period, necessitates an increased number of blocks to ensure adequate representation in the Hankel matrix as the

Fig. 12. Stability, damping diagrams and cumulative sum of the stable poles detected by the cov-SSI method (eight blocks) along period as a function of the signal sampling frequency.

sampling frequency increases. Fig. 12 illustrates the number of stable poles detected in the surge frequency band during test No. 154 as a function of the sampling frequency of the input signals. The analysis shown in Fig. 12 reveals that, for the same number of blocks, employing signals with higher sampling frequencies causes the cov-SSI method (as well as the other methods) to focus on identifying modes corresponding to very short time lags ($n_{\text{Blocks}} \cdot \Delta t$, in the current case). Consequently, more stable poles are detected at higher frequencies (i.e., within the short period range depicted in Fig. 12) compared to downsampled signals. This is explained by the effective time step being truncated.

Based on these observations, the input signals were downsampled by a factor of 30 ($f_s \approx 0.4$ Hz). This adjustment was made to target pole detection within the 12.5–190.0 s period range. However, it is important to note that a lower sampling frequency may reduce the energy content associated with the highest-frequency mode (e.g., the heave mode in the system under investigation). This reduced sampling frequency significantly enhances the computational efficiency of the direct method used to estimate the correlation functions. As a result, the direct method was selected over alternatives such as fast-Fourier-transform-based methods or the random decrement technique. While the random decrement method offers flexibility when calculating correlations at user-defined thresholds and permits the analysis of nonlinearities, it generates noisier correlation functions compared to the direct method, at least for the test durations considered in this study.

The influence of the number of blocks used in the SSI algorithms on the modal properties of the system was evaluated by comparing the synthesised system response to the simultaneous decay of the system's DOFs. The DOFs were subjected to an initial offset with an amplitude of unity. The analyses were performed on the downsampled signals, employing the sumMAC function as the automatic mode selection technique. The results showed no significant differences in the synthesised response across the models obtained. Based on the computational time required to perform the analysis (Fig. 13), a configuration of 40 blocks was selected for the SSI processes. This choice balanced computational efficiency with accuracy and stability of the identified modal properties.

The influence of the automatic mode selection strategies implemented in the EOMA software for the SSI methods on the synthesised system decay response is analysed in the following discussion. Fig. 14 presents the decay response of the system model synthesised using the ODSs identified from the cov-SSI analysis results. These results were obtained with configurations of 32 and 40 blocks, applying sumMAC and the clustering or distance-based functions and strategies available in EOMA (Galván, 2024).

Fig. 13. Computational performance of the cov-SSI method as a function of the number of blocks.

The reference natural frequencies and mode shapes used for evaluating the distance function were those determined through numerical methods, as summarized in Table 2. It should be noted that, since the identification process was conducted using degrees instead of radians, the reference mode shapes, when arranged into a matrix, form the identity matrix, I .

While the sumMAC function does not rely on any user-defined parameters, the clustering methods and stable pole selection strategies compare results against predefined user-defined modal parameters in the remaining strategies investigated here. The distance function used in this analysis (Eq. (11)) assigns weights of 0.1 and 1.0 to the frequency and mode shapes terms, respectively, to prioritise the latter in the evaluation process.

A comparison of the mildest and most energetic irregular wave sea states tested indicates that the minimum distance strategy produced the lowest deviations in the predicted decay responses. This suggests that the minimum distance approach is the most robust mode-tracking strategy for the scenarios considered. The sensitivity analyses performed demonstrate that a reasonable balance between computational efficiency and precision is achieved by using 40 blocks in conjunction with the minimum distance mode selection strategy.

4.2.2. Modeshapes tracking along different wave conditions

The evolution of the system's damped frequencies and damping ratios throughout the irregular wave tests conducted during the experimental campaign is presented in Fig. 15. The results are derived from three time-domain identification methods: LogDec, cov-SSI and dat-SSI. While the dat-SSI algorithm received the downsampled signals, cov-SSI was applied to the correlation matrix of these signals and LogDec only processed to the correlation functions in the diagonal. Consequently, comparisons with the damping ratios identified with the SSI methods may be inaccurate. For the SSI methods, mode tracking is performed using the minimum distance mode selection strategy, and consequently, no statistical parameters are associated with the results. In contrast, the LogDec method provides the extremes and mean and mean plus/minus one standard deviation of the modal parameters. For reference, Fig. 15 also includes the mean and mean plus/minus one standard deviation of the modal characteristics determined from the decay tests (Section 4.1). These values are computed considering the first three peaks and all peaks of the response, represented by the grey and green horizontal lines, respectively.

Fig. 15 demonstrates that the resonance frequencies of the system identified by the SSI methods exhibit low standard deviation across the experimental tests. However, the surge mode constitutes a notable exception, displaying a significant frequency shift towards higher values during tests involving waves with a 20.0 s peak period and a single test with a primary wave excitation at 14.0 s. This frequency shift may be attributed to the first longitudinal mode of the water free surface in the ECN wave tank, which is estimated to occur at 110.6 s (Fig. 11). Further analysis and comments on this unintended effect are provided in subsequent sections. In the meantime, the tests described above are excluded from the following discussion.

The peak detection algorithm employed by the LogDec method identifies shorter periods for the heave mode (Fig. 15(b)), detecting them at intervals of approximately 14.2 s. Consequently, the identified period corresponds to the main wave loading period rather than the resonance period of the heave mode. Although the algorithm could be adjusted to track the frequency of the reference mode, to improve the results, it has been preferred to show the limitations of this method.

For the surge mode, the largest mean damping ratio identified is below 20%, as determined with the LogDec method; a value of 15% is found via the SSI methods. The high standard deviation observed in the damping ratios may indicate nonlinear behaviour in the damping mechanism. When excluding cases where the surge frequency is influenced by external effects, the damping ratios determined by the SSI methods align with those obtained from the decay tests.

Fig. 14. Experimental normalised autocorrelations, R_{xx} (in black), and synthesised cov-SSI model response to unitary decay as a function of the automatic mode selection strategy: *sumMAC*, *clustering* and *minDistance*. Identification was performed using (a) 32 and (b) 40 blocks. The wave conditions (significant height and peak period) are 3.0 m, 10.0 s (test No. 154, left) and 12.0 m, 20.0 s (test No. 164, right).

The SSI methods reveal that the damping ratio of the heave mode remains below 5%, except in two tests with 20.0 s peak period waves, where the cov-SSI method identified higher damping values. The damping ratios are aligned with those calculated from the decay tests using the largest number of peaks/valleys available. The LogDec method, in contrast, determines significantly higher damping ratios during the test with a 14.0 s wave peak period; however, as noted earlier, this result reflects wave excitation rather than the heave resonance period of the system.

The pitch damping ratios identified are in general below 5%, yet still above the values determined from the decay tests. The damping ratios are correlated with the wave conditions, which is also observed for the yaw mode; in this case, the correlation is consistent across all methods.

The best agreement between the results of the LogDec and the SSI methods was observed for the yaw mode. This mode was found to be weakly excited throughout the tests due to the direction of the waves, thereby preserving the system's linearity even under severe wave conditions.

Despite the presence of certain discrepancies that can be attributed to differences in the hull and the SKS design, the identified damping ratios exhibit a comparable trend to that reported by [Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose \(2019\)](#), who employed the ITD method to a 10 MW FOWT with a semi-submersible-type floating substructure.

The FS modal properties of the ECN FOWT rigid-body DOFs determined using the different identification methods are presented in [Table 6](#) for the mildest sea state condition ($H_s = 3.0$ m and $T_p = 10.0$ s,

Fig. 15. Evolution of the statistics of the system's modal properties of the surge, heave, pitch and yaw DOFs across the experimental tests at ECN dedicated to only irregular waves conditions. (a) Damped frequency and (b) damping ratio, found using the LogDec, cov-SSI and dat-SSI methods. Horizontal lines indicate the values determined from the decays, employing the first three peaks and valleys (in green) and all the peaks and valleys available (in grey). The solid lines indicate the mean value while the dashed lines account for the standard deviation.

test No. 154). For the sake of simplicity, although the mode shapes are complex, only the magnitudes of the mode shapes are provided, as it has been done by other authors (Pimenta et al., 2020). As previously discussed, sway and roll have been excluded from the table due to the minimal wave excitation measured along the y-direction.

The findings demonstrate that satisfactory alignment of the system's natural periods is achieved through the utilisation of diverse identification methods. The differences between the LogDec and PQ methods are indicative of nonlinear damping behaviour. The mode shapes, damping and periods identified by the SSI methods demonstrate significant agreement with one to another. The most significant disparity pertains to the surge component of the yaw mode shape.

The evolution of the components of the surge, heave, pitch and yaw modes, as a function of peak period, for the various wave conditions examined are shown in Fig. 16. The results indicate the degree of coupling between the system's different DOFs. It is evident that the influence on the surge component of the pitch mode shape, $\phi_{5,1}$, is more

pronounced than on the pitch component of the surge mode shape, $\phi_{1,5}$. Consequently, the full 6×6 damping matrix is not symmetric.

4.2.3. The presence of free-surface modes in the wave basin

Identification of the deviations of the system's modal properties during the experimental campaign was significantly facilitated by implementing a mode tracker in the analysis of the experimental measurements. The detection of unexpected behaviour of the system dynamics was simple, as evinced in Fig. 15, which shows that the identified system surge resonance frequency is significantly higher in those tests that considered a 20.0 s wave peak period, irrespective of the significant wave height. Such long waves are in resonance with heave, and remarkably close to roll and pitch; thus, large radiation effects occurred. Shifting of the system surge period with the longest waves was also evident in the evolution of the surge response spectra (Fig. 17), supporting the behaviour seen in the previously presented autocorrelation functions (Fig. 14). The surge response spectra grouped by wave peak

Table 6

Modal properties (damped frequency f_d and period T_d , modal damping ratio ζ , and normalised modeshape's components) of the FOWT identified by applying different identification methods. Properties determined from low-pass filtered displacements recorded by the Qualysis system during the mildest sea state test.

Mode no.	DOF	Method	f_d	T_d	ζ	Modeshape's components [-]					
			[mHz]	[s]	[%]	Surge	Sway	Heave	Roll	Pitch	Yaw
1	Surge	LogDec	6.531	153.12	4.37	-	-	-	-	-	-
		PQ	6.531	153.12	4.35	-	-	-	-	-	-
		cov-SSI	6.541	152.88	3.60	1.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	-0.04	0.00
		dat-SSI	6.510	153.62	2.94	1.00	-0.03	0.00	0.00	-0.04	0.00
3	Heave	LogDec	47.801	20.92	1.35	-	-	-	-	-	-
		PQ	47.801	20.92	2.11	-	-	-	-	-	-
		cov-SSI	48.008	20.83	0.74	-0.01	0.00	-1.00	0.02	0.04	0.00
		dat-SSI	48.309	20.70	0.72	0.01	0.00	1.00	-0.02	-0.02	0.00
5	Pitch	LogDec	38.212	26.17	1.02	-	-	-	-	-	-
		PQ	38.212	26.17	1.75	-	-	-	-	-	-
		cov-SSI	37.893	26.39	1.10	0.01	0.00	0.05	-0.02	1.00	0.01
		dat-SSI	38.110	26.24	0.86	-0.02	0.00	0.02	0.01	-1.00	-0.01
6	Yaw	LogDec	14.476	69.08	2.80	-	-	-	-	-	-
		PQ	14.476	69.08	2.79	-	-	-	-	-	-
		cov-SSI	14.449	69.21	2.34	-0.32	-0.01	-0.01	-0.03	0.05	-1.00
		dat-SSI	14.507	68.93	2.69	0.01	-0.02	0.02	0.03	0.00	1.00

Fig. 16. Evolution of the normalised modal amplitude of the coupled DOFs of the (a) surge, (b) heave, (c) pitch and (d) yaw mode shapes as a function of wave peak period (test Nos. 154 to 164). Shown are the results from the cov-SSI (●) and dat-SSI (x) identification methods.

Fig. 17. Frequency content of the FOWT rigid-body surge response during irregular wave tests, grouped by T_p .

period in Fig. 17 show a secondary peak at around 115 s in some of the tests that considered 14.0 s peak period waves. Surge motion might have been excited by the energy contained in fluid's surface around 115 s (Fig. 11), which was identified with the free-surface mode (1, 0) of the basin. No energy developed in the surge spectrum above 200 s.

It is important to note that for the intermediate peak period waves in Fig. 17, the surge response presents a double-peak-shaped spectrum (at low frequency), with the main peak still very close to system's surge natural period, and a secondary peak around 115 s. Meanwhile, in the tests with the longest waves, a single peak (around 115 s) was observed, largely displaced from surge natural period of the FOWT, and indicative of different behaviour in the surge response. The surge response period shifted from the design one (close to 152.0 s) to approximately 115.0 s.

However, such a significant reduction in the surge period may be challenging to justify by an increase of the SKS-provided stiffness or a reduction of the added mass in the surge direction. Although the round-

robin test (Gueydon et al., 2021a) suggests that the measurement cable bundle may stiffen the system, it is believed that any significant modifications to the surge period (>20%) would have been explicitly reported by Gueydon et al. (2021b). Thus, the characteristics of the free-surface modes of the fluid contained in the wave basin have been the focus of the following study.

Considering the dimensions of the rectangular wave basin of ECN provided in Section 3.2, the first longitudinal mode ($m = 1, n = 0$) has a theoretical period, at FS, of 110.62 s. The natural periods of the free surface in the rectangular basin have been determined using Eq. (19):

$$T_{Basin,(m,n)} = \frac{2 \cdot \pi}{\sqrt{g \cdot D}} \left[\left(\frac{\pi \cdot m}{l} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\pi \cdot n}{w} \right)^2 \right]^{-1/2} \quad (19)$$

where m and n correspond to the node numbers in a mode along the longitudinal and transversal directions, respectively (Magdalena et al., 2022). The acceleration of gravity is denoted by g , l and w are the length

Fig. 18. Details of the low-frequency range of the stabilisation diagrams as a function of the SSI identification method and coloured by the irregular waves' T_p (10, 14 and 20 s). The vertical lines in cyan indicate the theoretical fluid free-surface modes' fundamental period, $T_{B,(n,m)}$, while the lines in brown indicate the FOWT's resonance period, T_i . (a) Model order and (b) damping ratio diagram. The cov- and dat-SSI method results are indicated by \bullet and \times , respectively.

Fig. 19. Same as Fig. 18 but for the wave-frequency range.

and width of the wave basin, respectively, and D denotes the water depth.

As illustrated in Fig. 11, ten distinct natural periods of the free-surface modes that fall within the system’s rigid-body dynamics period range are represented. The stability and damping diagrams of the stable poles identified by the SSI methods, grouped by the waves’ T_p , are presented in Figs. 18 and 19 at low- and wave-frequencies, respectively. As indicated by the vertical lines, the fundamental periods of the basin’s first 16 free-surface modes as well as the FOWT’s modes are presented. It should be noted that while a multitude of free-surface modes are situated within the wave-frequency region, only the most salient have been incorporated into the plots to avoid an overabundance of information.

In the low-frequency range, the experimental records clearly and distinctly depict the presence of the first longitudinal mode of the fluid free surface in the basin (Fig. 17), as evidenced by the cov-SSI- and dat-SSI-produced stability diagrams around 115.0 s. According to the results of these methods (Fig. 18), the free-surface mode (1, 0) is observed to be exclusively excited by 20.0 s peak period waves. The secondary peak in the spectrum of surge response around 115 s (Fig. 17), observed for 14.0 s peak period waves, is not clearly identified by these methods. The influence of this free-surface mode has also been observed in the heave response spectrum, where the amount of energy around the indicated period depends on the relative position of the model with respect to the free-surface mode shape (-8.0 m from the node position of the free-surface mode (1, 0), for the 50 m long basin of ECN).

To explain the influence of the wave’s T_p on the excitation of mode (1, 0), it should be noted that the resonance period of the free-surface mode (1, 3) is, theoretically, close to 22.0 s (Fig. 19). In addition to sharing the same mode shape along the longitudinal axis, free-surface modes (1, 3) and (1,0) are harmonic by a factor of 5. Thus, it is plausible that some energy was transferred to from mode (1, 3) to mode (1, 0), i.e., energy transmission between harmonics may be the mechanism behind the excitation of mode (1, 0). Then, while the relation $p = T_p / T_{Basin,(1,3)}$ approaches unity, it is expected to increase the excitation of

mode (1, 3) and mode (1, 0).

The latter would also indicate that while the energy of mode (1, 0) increases, the strength of the coupling between the fluid inside the basin and the model’s DOFs also increases. Surge is notably affected due to the shape of the free-surface mode but also due to its proximity in frequency. While the intermediate peak period wave ($p = 14/22$) surge spectrum in Fig. 17 shows a secondary peak due to mode (1, 0), the complexity of the basin–model coupled system increases for the longest peak period waves ($p \approx 1$). Under this peak period waves both, mode (1, 0) and the surge mode coalesce into synchronous motion with a period of 115 s, thus producing the shifted single peak in the surge response spectrum (Fig. 17). As it would be expected, the mass of water develops more energy than the system, and thus, free-surface mode (1, 0) dominates the coupled motion. This phenomenon may be attributed to frequency blockage due to complex modal interactions between the modes in this nonlinear system, i.e., the coupled system composed of the basin and the scaled model in this case. The progressive translation of the poles detected in the surge period range by the SSI methods towards $T_{Basin,(1,0)}$ (Fig. 18), may indicate a transition between three states where the model and basin systems’ free-surface mode (1, 0) would be uncoupled or weakly or tightly coupled ($T_p = \{10.0, 14.0, 20.0\}$ s, respectively). Although a hypothesis of the mechanism behind the shift of surge period has been given here, it is worth remembering that significant radiation and high-order wave loading occurs with high waves resonating at the FOWT’s heave period. However, to understand this phenomenon better, further investigations should be conducted.

At approximately 50.0 s, a persistent mode is also identified; however, its origin remains ambiguous. The mode is situated between the theoretical $T_{Basin,(2,1)}$ and $T_{Basin,(2,0)}$. A similar trend is observed at 30.0 s in Fig. 19; which in this case, is located between the increase of the longitudinal nodes number of the free-surface $T_{Basin,(1,2)}$ to $T_{Basin,(2,2)}$.

The subsequent discussion will centre on the near-resonance irregular waves, which exhibit a peak period (20.0 s) that closely corresponds

Fig. 20. Details of the low-frequency range of the stabilisation diagrams as a function of the SSI identification method and coloured by the irregular waves' H_s (6, 9 and 12 m) for the $T_p = 20.0$ s tests. The vertical lines in cyan indicate the theoretical fluid free-surface modes' fundamental period, $T_{B,(n,m)}$, while the lines in brown indicate the FOWT's resonance period, T_1 . (a) Model order and (b) damping ratio diagram. The cov- and dat-SSI method results are indicated by \bullet and \times , respectively.

Fig. 21. Same as Fig. 20, but for the wave-frequency range.

to the heave one. As illustrated in Figs. 20 and 21, the stability and damping diagrams for various significant wave heights, H_s , are presented, again in the low- and wave-frequency ranges of interest. The influence of the significant wave height on the damping ratio is

significant, as seen in the theoretical surge–sway resonance lines (Fig. 20 (b)). However, it is important to note that at 115.0 s ($T_{Basin,(1,0)}$) the surge damping estimates are lower than those found at original surge period for any of the wave heights analysed.

Fig. 22. Experimental normalised autocorrelation, R_{xx} , and synthesised model (cov-SSI and dat-SSI) response to unitary decay. The results are shown for a wave peak period of 20.0 s and significant wave heights of (a) 6.0 m, (b) 9.0 m and (c) 12.0 m.

By expanding the surge frequency band of interest (the shaded region around T_1 in the stability diagrams) to encompass the fluid free-surface longitudinal mode, the minimum distance automatic mode selection strategy selected a mode from that wider group, and the predicted response by the synthesised OMA model notably improved in capturing the dynamic behaviour of the system (Fig. 22). This finding aligns with the low surge damping ratio estimated by Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019) to match experiments and numerical predictions (see Fig. 2). Note that the ζ_1 found at around 115.0 s is nearly doubled at 150.0 s for the largest wave height case (Fig. 20(b)). These are important discrepancies that are expected to impact the predicted surge response substantially.

Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019) using ITD method found that heave, roll and pitch damping were low, in line with the estimations found in this work. However, those damping estimations were far from the values needed by Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019) to calibrate their numerical results ($\zeta_5 > 40\%$ with wave peak periods studied far enough from the closest system rigid-body resonance period).

Nevertheless, a notable distinction emerges when contrasting the Nautilus concept, explored by Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019), with the DeltaWind concept analysed in this study. The former incorporates an additional column that pierces the surface, accompanied by significantly larger heave plates. This configuration could justify such substantial damping values, particularly in the context of severe sea conditions.

In this section, it has been suggested that the FOWT's objective surge resonance period shifted due to complex nonlinear interactions between the free-surface mode (1, 0), FOWT surge mode and highly nonlinear wave loading. The strength of the coupling between the enclosed fluid in the basin and model, with the waves' peak period at heave resonance, has been related to the excitation level of mode (1, 3) of the free surface, which is a harmonic of mode (1,0) and should eventually transmit energy to the latter.

Regarding the performance of the OMA methods, by altering the mode shape tracking setup (Section 4.2.2), and by opening the surge frequency band of interest (and notably reducing α in Eq. (11)), the SSI methods are capable of capturing the influenced FOWT surge response, even under extreme sea states at the resonance heave period ($H_S = 12.0$ m and $T_P = 20.0$ s). The updated surge damping ratio associated with the new surge mode shape identified around 115.0 s aligns with the numerical damping required by Pegalajar-Jurado and Bredmose (2019) to minimize the standard deviation of the surge response. This observation suggests that the ITD identification method employed in the aforementioned study may have captured a distinct surge mode, potentially obscured by free-surface interactions and/or spurious wave reflections. However, the uncertainty associated with the SKS-introduced damping, as the authors pointed out, under wave conditions may justify the identification of such high damping values by the identification algorithm.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the FS identification of FOWT dynamics is performed from scaled laboratory model measurements. The 10 MW FOWT model under scrutiny was moored by an aerial SKS with constant surge stiffness characteristics, a measure that served to reduce the overall uncertainty during testing. In-depth characterisation of the modal properties across decay and irregular wave tests, and an analysis of the influence of the basin's free-surface modes, was conducted to determine a plausible cause of hydrodynamic loading underestimation at low frequencies returned by numerical models, as reported in the literature.

Novel damping contours were constructed from decay tests to determine the hydrodynamic damping mechanisms and the dependence on cross-coupled DOFs. A methodology utilising signal filtering based on system physics was employed to derive the complete 6×6 damping matrix. The simple LogDec method supported by stability conditions, in

both its linear and quadratic forms, was utilised to analyse the decay test records. In addition, higher complexity OMA methods (cov-SSI and dat-SSI) were utilised to analyse the results from irregular wave tests. To identify the FOWT's modal properties automatically across the various tests, the EOMA software was augmented with mode tracking capability, and the optimal setup of these methods was studied. To validate the modal characteristics of the rigid-body DOFs of the FOWT identified by these methods, the synthesised model response to decay was compared with autocorrelation functions. Thereby, the tool established in this work provides a foundation for the development of digital twins based on metocean conditions and operation-state-dependent linearised models. However, further development is necessary to address the flexibility of components in a more complex and fully operational FOWT model, and to provide comprehensive SHM capabilities.

By means of the mode tracker, significant variation in the surge modal characteristics across the experiments with irregular waves was observed. The surge period was found to significantly shift (by -32%) towards lower values when the system was subjected to 20.0 s peak period waves, for all of the significant wave heights studied. Modification of the system response, as identified by the SSI methods, was also confirmed through the surge response spectrum and the autocorrelation functions.

Further investigations revealed that, for the scale tested, the shortened surge period (from 152 to 115 s) matched the fundamental free-surface mode (1, 0) of the fluid enclosed in the wave basin. It was found that the presence of the free-surface mode (1, 0) increases as a function of the waves' peak period (10, 14 and 20 s). The presence of this mode was also evident in the spectrum of the wave elevation in the tests without the model installed, resulting in excitation of mode (1, 0). Apparently, the longest period free-surface mode involved may be receiving energy due to the harmonics linked to the motion of the free-surface mode (1, 3), whose natural frequency is very close to the wave peak period of 20 s and heave resonance. This energy has been shown to interfere with the response of the FOWT, seemingly masking the original surge mode or attracting the surge response as a kind of frequency blockage, due to complex interactions between free-surface modes and the FOWT's modes.

Across the wave periods studied, a transition in the surge behaviour was glimpsed through the shape of the spectrum at low frequencies. From the shortest to the longest wave tests, the shape of the surge spectrum evolved from a single peak with the main peak located at the surge period, to a double-peak shape where the free-surface mode (1, 0) appeared in the spectrum. Finally, under the longest wave conditions, surge spectrum presents a single peak again but located at mode (1, 0) natural period instead of surge period, coalescing surge and free-surface mode (1, 0). This transition might evince the evolution of the coupling strength between the basin and model system. The study of waves with a peak period above the period of the free-surface mode (1, 3) may contribute to determining the full transition of the system's response, and thus, further investigations should be conducted to understand this phenomenon better.

It has been demonstrated that OMA methods are capable of reproducing the experimental correlation functions, even under extreme sea states with peak periods occurring close to the system's heave resonance. The mode tracker has been a useful tool for detecting deviations of the modal properties of the FOWT's rigid-body modes. Stability and damping diagrams were also employed to understand the evolution of these properties as a function of sea state, and to detect and confirm the presence of free-surface modes in the wave basin. The evolution of the ODS components with the sea state revealed that these captured the system's forced response and showed a higher degree of coupling for increased wave loading. The ODSs exhibited greater sensitivity to the peak period than to the significant wave height.

We would like to point out that when numerically replicating wave basin tests, generally the aim is to reproduce open-sea conditions, and therefore, the free-surface modes of the physical basin are lost. This

additional energy in the physical tank is not modelled in numerical investigations. This may explain why for more energetic sea states the underprediction of numerical simulation increases, even under constrained model configurations using CFD. Thus, the identification of free-surface modes and/or wave reflections is of particular importance in numerical model calibration tasks.

The present work has focused on the hydrodynamics of FOWTs. Given that the model was reduced to a rigid-body system, it may be possible to draw conclusions that are applicable to other floating systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Josean Galván: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **José M. Domínguez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Joseba Albizuri:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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